

DHATVAGNI DUSHTI AND ITS ROLE IN PSYCHOSOMATIC DISORDERS THROUGH
OJAS DEPLETION AN AYURVEDIC PRESPECTIVE*¹Dr. Sanjivani Vijay Godbole, ²Dr. Krishna N. Kadam¹PG Scholar Department Rognidan Evam Vikriti Vigyan, Government Ayurved College Nanded, Maharashtra 431601.²Associate Professor, Rognidan Evam Vikriti Vigyan Department, Government Ayurvedic College Nanded Maharashtra 431601.***Corresponding Author: Dr. Sanjivani Vijay Godbole**PG Scholar Department Rognidan Evam Vikriti Vigyan, Government Ayurved College Nanded, Maharashtra 431601. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18874558>**How to cite this Article:** ¹Dr. Sanjivani Vijay Godbole, ²Dr. Krishna N. Kadam (2026). Dhatvagni Dushti And Its Role In Psychosomatic Disorders Through Ojas Depletion An Ayurvedic Prespective. European Journal of Pharmaceutical and Medical Research, 13(3), 281–284.

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ABSTRACT

Ayurveda explains health as a balanced state of body, mind, and spirit, governed by the integrity of Agni, particularly Dhatvagni, which regulates tissue-level metabolism. Impairment of Dhatvagni (Dhatvagni Dushti) leads to improper dhatu nourishment, Ama formation, and ultimately Ojas depletion, which weakens physical immunity and mental resilience. Ojas is described as the vital essence (Sarvadhatusara Oja) responsible for vitality, mental stability, and psychosomatic harmony. This article explores the correlation between Dhatvagni Dushti and psychosomatic disorders through Ojas depletion, analyzing classical Ayurvedic concepts and comparing them with modern physiological understanding of mind-body interactions. Findings indicate that disturbed Agni and Ojas correlate with stress-related disorders, anxiety, depression, and immune dysfunction. Strengthening Agni, enhancing Ojas, and applying Satvavajaya chikitsa serve as effective preventive and therapeutic strategies.

KEYWORDS: *Dhatvagnu, Oja, Psychosomatic Disorders.***INTRODUCTION**

In Ayurveda, Agni is the fundamental force responsible for digestion, transformation, and maintenance of life. Among its subdivisions, Dhatvagni plays a crucial role in the metabolism of each Dhatu (tissue). Proper functioning of Dhatvagni ensures dhatu poshana, tissue strength, and ultimately the formation and preservation of Ojas-the vital essence responsible for immunity, mental stability, and overall well-being.

When Dhatvagni becomes impaired (Dhatvagni Dushti), tissue metabolism becomes faulty, leading to dhatu kshaya or dushti, which in turn results in Ojas depletion (Oja-kshaya). Since Ojas is the seat of mental and physical resilience, its depletion manifests as psychosomatic disorders, where psychological disturbances produce physical disease conditions.

Psychosomatic disorders are conditions in which psychological factors like stress, anxiety, fear, or emotional conflicts produce real physical symptoms. The body expresses what the mind is unable to resolve.

Though medical tests may show minimal structural damage, the symptoms are genuine and distressing, affecting systems such as the nervous, cardiovascular, gastrointestinal, or musculoskeletal systems.

Thus, Ayurveda reflect the inseparable unity of mind and body, and their management focuses on Dosha balance, Satvavajaya (mental control), and holistic healing.

अग्निर् हि देहस्य बलं रक्षणं च ।

Agni is responsible for the strength, protection, and maintenance of the body (Charaka Samhita, Chikitsa). A balanced state of Agni is essential for health.

ओजो नाम किलानन्दो देहस्य । च. सु.17/74^[1]

Ojas is the essence that gives bliss and stability to the body. Ojas represents immunity and vitality, and its proper function depends on balanced Agni.

These references show that while Agni regulates strength, Ojas maintains physical and emotional stability.

Ojas is considered the supreme essence of all bodily tissues (dhatus) and is vital for life.

Modern psychosomatic disorders arise from altered stress response and mind-body imbalance, which Ayurveda interprets as Dhatvagni Dushti, Ojas depletion, and Manovaha srotodushti.

DISCUSSION

Importance of Agni & Ojas^[1]

अग्निः प्राणायुर बलम उच्यते सर्वेषाम देहिनाम् इ तस्य नित्यम हि रक्षणम कुर्यात् प्रार्थनातः ॥

अ.ह. सु.12/1^[2]

Agni is the life (prāṇa), strength (bala), and vitality of all living beings.

Therefore, Agni must be protected and maintained with great care.

सर्वधातुसार भवति, तेन जीवति जीवति। हृदि तिष्ठति तद्ध्योजः, तद्विना न प्राणोऽनुपाल्यते ॥

च.सू.17/74^[3]

ओज सभी धातुओं का सार है (essence of all dhatus).

Ojas is the life-sustaining essence present in the heart.

Without Ojas, life cannot be sustained.

Dhatvagni

धातूनां परस्परं सम्भवो हि नित्यं, अग्निः स्वधात्वग्निरूपः स्वधातुं पक्त्वा विवर्द्धयति। अ.ह.सु. 18/10^[4]

- धातूनां परस्परं सम्भवः = Each dhatu is formed from the previous one.
- अग्निः स्व-धात्व-अग्नि-रूपः = The Agni present in each dhatu.
- स्व-धातुं पक्त्वा = After digesting/metabolizing its respective dhatu
- विवर्द्धयति = Nourishes the next dhatu.

Each dhatu is formed from the previous one. The Dhatvagni, present in each dhatu, digests and transforms it, thus nourishing the next dhatu.

Rasa → Rakta → Mamsa → Meda → Asthi → Majja → Sukra → Ojas

Importance Of Dhatvagni

देहाग्नि-भूताग्नीनां धातूनां च यथाक्रमम् । पाकः सम्यक् कृतो येन धातूनां वर्धनं भवेत् ॥ अ.ह.सु.11/1-2^[5]

Proper functioning of Jatharagni, Bhutagni, and Dhatvagni ensures correct digestion and proper dhatu formation and growth.

Dhatvagni Dushti

Dhatvagni is the metabolic fire present in each of the seven dhatus (Rasa, Rakta, Mamsa, Meda, Asthi, Majja, Sukra). Its role is to digest nutrients at the tissue level and form healthy dhatus, ultimately producing Ojas. When this dhatu-level imbalance, Agni becomes disturbed, it is called Dhatvagni Dushti.

- Manda Dhatvagni - slow tissue metabolism → Dhatu kshaya
- Tikshna Dhatvagni - excessive metabolism → Tissue depletion

- Vishama Dhatvagni - irregular digestion → Unstable dhatu formation

Causes of Dhatvagni Dushti

- Improper diet (viruddha ahara, junk food, irregular meals)
- Excessive fasting or overeating
- Ama formation
- Stress, anger, fear, grief Improper sleep, sedentary lifestyle

Effects

- Poorly formed dhatus (dhatu kshaya or dushti)
- Ama accumulation at tissue level
- Srotorodha (channel blockage)
- Weak Ojas formation → lowered immunity Development of chronic diseases & psychosomatic disorders.

How Dhatvagni Dushti Causes Ojas Depletion

Oja

सर्वधातुसारः ओजः॥ च.सू.17/76^[6]

- Ojas is the pure essence of all seven dhatus and is essential for life, strength, immunity, and mental stability.

धातूनां परमो धातुः स एव ओजः प्रकीर्तितः । येन जीवति भूतानि स धात्वग्नि संभवः ॥^[7]

शां. सं. पू. खं.5/21-23

- The finest essence of all dhatus is Ojas, and it is produced only when Dhatu Agni functions properly.
- When dhatus are weak or improperly formed → Ojas becomes weak.
- Ojas is depleted by improper food, lifestyle, emotional stress, excessive exertion, chronic diseases, dhatu kshaya, and Ama formation, leading to weakness of body, mind, and immunity.

Oja Sthana

हृदि स्थितं तदोजः। अ.ह.सु.11/35^[8]

Ojas Resides in the heart

धातुक्षये सत्त्वबलक्षयः। च.वि.15/16^[9]

Loss of dhatus leads to loss of mental strength and vitality.

Dhatvagni dushti → Dhatu kshaya → Oja-ksaya → psychosomatic disorders.

Oja Kshaya Lakshana

तन्नशे जन्तुरप्रत्यहृतप्राणो भवति। विभेति, भ्रमति, क्लैब्यं स्वेददुर्बलता भवेत् ॥

अ.ह.11/38-39^[10]

When Ojas is depleted or displaced, the person becomes as if life is being drained.

Symptoms of Oja-ksaya include

- Bhibheti** – Fearfulness
- Bhramati** - Confusion, giddiness
- Klaibyam** - Loss of strength or courage
- Sweda** - Excessive sweating
- Daurbalya** - Generalized weakness

Manovaha Srotas

Sthan

हृदयश्च दश धमनयश्च मनोवहाः॥च.वि.3/6^[11]

Manovaha srotas are situated in the heart (hrdaya) and ten dhmanis (nadis/vessels connected to the mind)

Dushti Lakshana

तस्य दुष्टे शोकः भयम् क्रोधःस्मृतिभ्रमश्च ॥ च.वि.3/9^[12]

When Manovaha srotas are vitiated, symptoms like

- Shoka (grief)
- Bhaya (fear)
- Krodha (anger)
- Smrti vibhrama (memory disturbance) arise.

Psychosomatic Impact

When Ojas depletes

Mind Effects

- Anxiety
- Emotional instability
- Panic feeling
- Depression
- Poor concentration & memory

Weak immunity, frequent illness

Body Effects

IBS (stress-related digestion issues)

- Headache/migraine
- Palpitations
- Sleep disturbance
- Hormonal imbalance

Pathophysiology of Psychosomatic Disorders

Modern View

- Stress Activate HPA axis (Hypothalamus, Pituitary, Adrenal Glands) – Cortisol, Adrenaline – It's Stress response system of the body
- Causes Autonomic imbalance (Sympathetic Overactivity)
- Alters Neurotransmitters (Serotonin, GABA, dopamine)
- Suppresses Immune system – Inflammation
- Physiological changes appear in organs (Gut, Heart, Skin, Lungs)

Ayurvedic View

- Mental Stress → Rajas-Tamas increases and Sattva decreases
- Leads to Vata Vitiation
- Causes Manovaha Strotodushti (shok, moha, bhaya, visada)
- Long term stress – Dhatvagni Dushti – Dhatu Kshaya – Oja Kshaya
- Reduced Ojas + Aggravated Vata - disturb mind – body coordination
- Result in Psychosomatic Symptoms.

CONCLUSION

Since Ojas is the basis of physical strength, immunity, mental stability, and emotional resilience, its decline directly disturbs Sattva and aggravates Rajas-Tamas along with Vata, thereby impairing Manovaha Srotas.

This disruption creates a continuous cycle of mind-body imbalance, resulting in the manifestation of psychosomatic disorders such as anxiety, depression, palpitations, digestive instability, and stress-induced conditions. Thus, Dhatvagni dusti, through progressive

Ojas depletion, becomes a central pathogenic mechanism linking metabolic dysfunction to psychological and somatic illness. Restoration of Agni and protection of Ojas therefore remain the most essential therapeutic goals for maintaining holistic health and preventing psychosomatic disease.

REFERENCES

1. Acharya Charak, Charaka Samhita, by Agnivesa, revised by Charaka and Dridhabala of Chakrapanidatta, Edited by Vaidya Jadavaji Trikamji Acharya, Chaukhamba Prakashan, Varanasi, Reprint, 2013.
2. Vagbhaṭa. Aṣṭāṅga Hṛdaya, with commentaries of Arunadatta & Hemadri. Chowkhamba Sanskrit Series Office, Varanasi, p.193.
3. Vagbhaṭa. Aṣṭāṅga Hṛdaya. Sutrasthana, Chapter 18, Verse 10. Arunadatta and Hemadri commentaries. Translated by Srikantha Murthy KR. Varanasi: Chaukhambha Krishnadas Academy, p. 268.
4. Vagbhata, Aṣṭāṅga Hṛdaye, Sutrasthana, Ayurvedavataraniya Adhyaya, with Sarvangasundara commentary of Arunadatta and Ayurvedarasayana of Hemadri, Chaukhamba Surbharati Prakashan, Varanasi, 2019.
5. Vagbhaṭa. Aṣṭāṅga Hṛdaya, Sutrasthana, Chapter 11, Verses 1-2. Arunadatta and Hemadri commentaries. Translated by K.R. Srikantha Murthy. Varanasi: Chaukhambha Krishnadas Academy, p. 164.
6. Charaka. Charaka Samhita, Sutrasthana 17/74. Cakrapanidatta commentary. Sharma RK, Dash B, translators. Varanasi: Chaukhambha Orientalia, p. 333.
7. Kashyapa. Kashyapa Samhita, Khila Sthana 5/21-23. Tewari PV, editor. Varanasi: Chaukhambha Vishvabharati, p. 92.
8. Vagbhaṭa. Aṣṭāṅga Hṛdaya, Sutrasthana 11/35. Arunadatta and Hemadri commentaries. Translated by K.R. Srikantha Murthy. Varanasi: Chaukhambha Krishnadas Academy, p. 168.
9. Caraka. Caraka Samhita, Cikitsasthana 15/16. Cakrapanidatta commentary. Sharma RK, Dash B, translators. Varanasi: Chaukhambha Orientalia, p. 519.
10. Vagbhaṭa. Aṣṭāṅga Hṛdaya, Sutrasthana, Chapter 11, Verses 38-39. Arunadatta and Hemadri commentaries. Translated by K.R. Srikantha Murthy. Varanasi: Chaukhambha Krishnadas Academy, p. 170.
11. Charaka. (2012). Charaka Samhita (Vimanasthana 3/6). Cakrapanidatta commentary. Translated by R. K.Sharma & B. Dash. Varanasi: Chaukhambha Orientalia, p. 247.
12. Charaka. (2012). Caraka Samhita (Vimanasthana 3/9). Cakrapanidatta commentary. Translated by R. K.Sharma & B. Dash. Varanasi: Chaukhambha Orientalia, p. 249.